

JS 44 (Rev. 04/21)

CIVIL COVER SHEET

Plaintiff(s): Takayuki Ueda

Defendant(s): OpenAI, L.P. and Greg Brockman

Basis of Jurisdiction: 1. U.S. Government Plaintiff

Citizenship of Principal Parties: N/A (Pro Se)

Nature of Suit: 890 - Other Statutory Actions

Origin: 1. Original Proceeding

Cause of Action: 28 U.S.C. § 1331 - Constitutional and Structural Harm

Requested in Complaint: Declaratory and Injunctive Relief

Jury Demand: Yes

Signature: /s/ Takayuki Ueda

Date: 09/26/2025